

Metadata of the list of alien taxa for South Africa

Background to this document

This is the metadata for the list of alien taxa for South Africa as part of the report series 'The status of biological invasions and their management in South Africa'. For the latest version of the report see <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7414803> for general details see <http://iasreport.sanbi.org.za>

The list of alien taxa itself will be in the general file name of 'A_list_of_alien_taxa_for_South_Africa_vYYYYMMDD.xlsx'. The file is stored as an Excel spreadsheet. This is in part as that format includes italics (in particular for scientificName), and also so it is more easily accessible for users of the report.

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A description of the indicators used in the report and guidance on some of the coding of confidence levels was outlined by Wilson et al. (2018). For updated factsheets go to: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13251> and navigate to the latest version. If there are discrepancies between the metadata and the indicator factsheets, please send through a note to the e-mail address above.

Documents that explain the Darwin core fields used are available at: <http://rs.gbif.org/> & <https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/>

If there are multiple values in any field, these are separated by a pipe-delimiter '|' with no spaces (e.g., `releaseInNature|escapeFromConfinement`). If values are nested then a colon is used to separate the main category from sub-categories (e.g., for pathways, `releaseInNature:biologicalControl`). When there are multiple values in any field, the confidence must either be in the same order as the values or specify the values (e.g., `high(releaseInNature:biologicalControl)|medium(escapeFromConfinement:research)`).

If there are multiple values in a field and want to select only some of them, can use `"=FIND("KZN";[@RangeBroad])"` and then sort or filter the dataset by this new column.

The value NA [which means not available (as per R)] is used either:

- where there is no information in a cell;
- there is some uncertainty as to whether effort has been made to find the value;
- information has been looked for and not found; or
- there is no applicable value for that cell.

The interpretation of NA should be given in the specific field in this document.

In some cases NE is used to mean Not Evaluated (e.g., in IUCN assessments like the Red List and EICAT). This can be because either the status report team has not evaluated it or that nobody has.

These metadata are only for continental South Africa, there are similar but discrete metadata and lists for the Prince Edward Islands (two sub-Antarctic islands that are part of South Africa), see <https://zenodo.org/record/8047695> and go to the latest version.

Details of how the list of alien taxa is produced are presented in a workflow that accompanies the report (go to <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047682> and access the latest version). The process of updating the list of alien taxa involves the creation of interim files. In some cases on the interim files, the fields 'isNative' or 'occurrenceStatus' are scored as 'check'. Until these issues are resolved the taxon will not be incorporated into the list of alien taxa. The interim files are available on request.

REFERENCING AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

References used in the list of alien taxa are available here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17185375>

Broadly following the reference style of PenSoft

<https://neobiota.pensoft.net/about#CitationsandReferences>.

In the list of alien taxa itself sources are cited: one author Winzer (2023); two authors: Zengeya and Faulkner (2001), Three or more authors: Miza et al. (1998). When more than one source is cited they are separated by pipe-delimiters.

For a web-site or database: 'BODATSA (12 April 2023)'; or 'GBIF.org (12 April 2023)'. A specific data download can be written in full in the source column 'GBIF.org (24 January 2022)

<https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.5fswvr>, though this is not essential. In all cases there should be a generic reference to the source in the bibliography. By contrast a generic web-site column would be written as: 'The Barcode of Life Data System (12 April 2023)', with the details and link in the bibliography: 'The Barcode of Life Data System v4 (2023). <https://www.boldsystems.org/>'.

Potentially a note can be made as to how the database was searched "A search was done using the search term: 'South Africa"Genus species' on the web-site

https://www.boldsystems.org/index.php/Public_BINSearch?searchtype=records"

REFERENCE FOR THIS DOCUMENT

SANBI and CIB (YYYY) Metadata of the list of alien taxa for South Africa. Part of the report series 'The Status of Biological Invasions and their Management in South Africa'. South African National Biodiversity Institute (Kirstenbosch) and Centre for Invasion Biology (Stellenbosch)

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433112>

Note: the doi directs the viewer to the latest version of the file. If a specific version is to be referenced, then the doi of that version should be used (available at the above link).

REFERENCE FOR THE SPECIES LIST

SANBI and CIB (YYYY) A list of alien taxa for South Africa. Part of the report series 'The Status of Biological Invasions and their Management in South Africa'. South African National Biodiversity Institute (Kirstenbosch) and Centre for Invasion Biology (Stellenbosch)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433102>

Note: the doi directs the viewer to the latest version of the file. If a specific version is to be referenced, then the doi of that version should be used (available at the above link).

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scientificName

Question addressed: What is the valid scientific name of the taxon?

Description: The binomial name of the taxon (normally at species level) including the authority as per dwc:scientificName. The choice of whether to include details of subspecific or supraspecific entities is due to data availability and in some cases regulatory listings.

Darwin Core: dwc:scientificName

Type: Character or NA in cases where there is a taxon that is required to be included in the report (e.g., as it is regulated) but that does not have a valid scientificName. In cases where a whole taxon is referred to (e.g., a whole genus) then it should be written as '*Genus* Authority'

taxonRank

Question addressed: The taxonomic rank of the most specific name in the scientificName.

Description: This provides information as to the level of identification given in the scientificName

Darwin Core: dwc:taxonRank

Type: Factor with eight or more levels, note can be higher level than genus

Value	Definition
fam.	Family
gen.	Genus
sect.	Section (between genus and subspecies)
gx.	Grex (used for flocks of orchids)
complex	Species complex
sp.	Species (will be for most taxa)
subsp.	Sub-species
cv.	Cultivar
f.	Forma (form)
var.	Varietas (variety)
biotype	Biotype
strain	Strain

scientificNameSource

Description: The taxonomic backbone used for the scientificName. An 'accessed date' should be provided if the information came from a database, and a web-link as appropriate. Note that the full reference will be included in the bibliography. See the section "REFERENCING AND BIBLIOGRAPHY" at the start of this document for more details

Type: Factor, number of levels will vary over time

Values: The following is a non-exhaustive list of sources used for nomenclature. If a source is added (in particular if not listed as below) make sure that the full reference is included in the accompanying reference list for the species list.

In general for plants the backbone used is the botanical database of Southern Africa (BODATSA). For all non-plant taxa the backbone used is the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). However, for many taxa these are not sufficient, in particular BODATSA only includes names of alien plant species found outside of captivity or cultivation and there are often delays between a change in

nomenclature and an update processed in GBIF (if such updates are fed through). The value NA is possible for example for regulated species that are not valid taxa, or for hybrids.

Value	Scope	Description and link
BODATSA	Native plants Alien plants found outside of captivity or cultivation	The botanical database of Southern Africa, http://posa.sanbi.org/ . Annual updates published as the South African National Plant Checklist.
GBIF.org	All taxa (not to be used for plant taxa in this database)	Global Biodiversity Information Facility, https://www.gbif.org/ . GBIF in turn uses various other primary sources for nomenclature, but the goal is not to list these here.
POWO	All plants. To be used primarily for taxa not found in BODATSA. Conflicts between BODATSA and POWO are to be resolved on a case by case basis	Plants of the World Online, https://powo.science.kew.org/ .
IPNI	All plants, should feed through to POWO and BODATSA but there can be delays	The International Plant Name Index (IPNI), https://www.ipni.org/ .
name_not_resolved	All taxa	There is on-going confusion around the name, e.g., a species complex or similar that has not been resolved.
Nemaplex	Nematodes not found in GBIF	THE "NEMATODE-PLANT EXPERT INFORMATION SYSTEM" A Virtual Encyclopedia on Soil and Plant Nematodes. http://nemaplex.ucdavis.edu/ http://nemaplex.ucdavis.edu/Uppermnus/genspecsearch.htm .
WoRMS	Marine taxa not found in GBIF	The World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) aims to provide an authoritative and comprehensive list of names of marine organisms, including information on synonymy. https://www.marinespecies.org/ .
Zachariades_2021_African_Entomology	Biological control agents released on plants, names not currently in GBIF	https://doi.org/10.4001/003.029.1077 .

Example:

BODATSA (12 April 2023)|POWO (12 April 2023)

or if a link is included,

BODATSA (12 April 2023) <http://posa.sanbi.org/sanbi/record/details/6526ca7f-a2d5-4a47-ac09-f72dc5194838>|POWO (12 April 2023)
<https://powo.science.kew.org/taxon/urn:lsid:ipni.org:names:469663-1>

scientificNameVerbatium

Description: the name exactly as it was provided in the scientificNameSource. It differs from otherNamesUsed as it does not include historical names that are no longer used in the scientificNameSource, and might be identical to scientificName.

Type: Character or NA, can be several values separated by a pipe delimiter. The full names including authorities should be added, including cases where there were typos.

otherNamesUsed

Description: Synonyms, names misapplied, or names for which there were typos or no authority provided in the original source. These might have appeared in the regulations or in one of the data sources used. The names in this column have been incorporated into scientificName based on the scientificNameSource used. It is not intended to be a complete list of synonyms for a particular taxon but is a pragmatic list so that people can search for taxa that they might think are otherwise missing. Information on what was done is available in the intermediate data file for a particular source (see the workflow).

Type: Character or NA, can be several values separated by a pipe delimiter. The full names including authorities should be added, including cases where there were typos.

kingdom

Description: The full scientific name of the kingdom in which the taxon is classified. The values are as per GBIF. *Incertae sedis* is Latin for 'of uncertain placement'.

Darwin Core: dwc:kingdom

Type: Factor, NA is not a possible value

Values: Animalia, Archaea, Bacteria, Chromista, Fungi, Plantae, Protozoa, Viruses, incertae sedis

Note: the values given here (and for phylum, class, order, and family) should not be regarded as authoritative as they are not automatically updated. The values are merely presented for user convenience. If these are to be used for any practical purpose, please refer back to the appropriate taxonomic backbone. The values presented were taken from GBIF, but the date on which this happened is not captured.

phylum

Description: The full scientific name of the phylum or division in which the taxon is classified.

Darwin Core: dwc:phylum

Type: Factor, NA is not a possible value

Values: (examples) Chordata (phylum), Bryophyta (division)

Note: see note under kingdom

class

Description: The full scientific name of the class in which the taxon is classified.

Darwin Core: dwc:class

Type: Factor, NA is a possible value if the value is not available on the relevant taxonomic source used

Values: (examples) Mammalia, Hepaticopsida

Note: see note under kingdom

order

Description: The full scientific name of the order in which the taxon is classified, the order level classification should be as per POWO for plants or as per GBIF.

Darwin Core: dwc:order

Type: Character, NA is a possible value if the value is not available on the relevant taxonomic source used

Note: see note under kingdom

family

Description: The full scientific name of the family in which the taxon is classified, the family level classification should be as per POWO for plants or as per GBIF.

Darwin Core: dwc:family

Type: Character, NA is a possible value if the value is not available on the relevant taxonomic source used

Note: see note under kingdom

vernacularName

Question addressed: What is the taxon commonly known as in South Africa?

Description: This is intended to be the predominant common name used to describe the taxon in South Africa. The common name used is generally the English common name, recognising that more than one English common name may exist, and that common names in other South African official languages also exist. Exceptions are made when a non-English common name is predominantly or exclusively used to describe a species (e.g., in the case of *Acacia cyclops*, the common name “rooikrans” is used in preference to the English “red eye”).

Darwin Core: dwc:vernacularName

Type: Character, or NA if no common name was found in usage. Lower case should be used throughout except for proper nouns.

RegulatoryListing

Question addressed: Is the taxon regulated as an alien species under South African law?

Description: The listing as per the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations of 2020. Ref: Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries (2020) National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act, 2004 (Act no. 10 of 2004): Alien and Invasive Species Lists. Government Gazette, Pretoria, 31–77 pp.

Note: the exact wording of the listing might be different from the scientificName (e.g., *Acacia decurrens* Willd. Is listed as ‘*Acacia decurrens* Willd. And hybrids, varieties and selections’); context-specific only refers to variation in the listing specified in the ‘categories’ field (e.g., in the regulations *A. decurrens* is listed in the category field only as “2”, but in the exemptions field it is listed as “Exempted for an existing plantation”, this is not regarded as context-specific here). In the 2014 and 2016 lists certain taxa were listed as prohibited (i.e. they were not present in the country and were not allowed to be introduced), however this prohibited list has since been removed.

If a taxon is not present in the country it is (or should be) regarded as unlisted, unless there is a discrepancy in the regulatory lists.

If the taxon is only described at a higher level than that at which the taxon is regulated then it is scored as uncertain. For example, there is a record of a dermestid from the Prince Edward Islands but only *Trogoderma granarium* is listed.

If the taxon is listed on the Prince Edward Islands only, then it would not be included in this dataset. For those cases, see the Prince Edward Islands species list and metadata.

Darwin Core: see extension <http://rs.gbif.org/vocabulary/gisin/2.0/regulatory.xml>, but the allowed vocabulary is specific to South Africa.

Relevant indicator(s): 4.1, 4.2–4.9

Type: Factor with 9 levels

Value	Definition
1a	
1b	
2	
3	
Context-specific	Taxa that are listed in different categories depending on the area or ecosystem in which they are found and/or for which there are specific exemptions and/or prohibitions.
Not.listed	Taxa that are not listed under the version of the NEM:BA A&IS Lists as specified above. It can be assumed that they were never previously listed or formally proposed for listing (see categories below).
Not.listed:was.listed	Taxa that have in the past been listed, but are not currently listed.
Not.listed:was.proposed	Taxa that have in the past been formally proposed for listing (i.e., in a list published in the government gazette), but that were never formally listed.
Uncertain	The taxon might be listed, but the identity of the taxon is at a higher level than the regulatory listing, i.e., it is not clear whether the taxon is actually listed or not.

regulatoryGrouping

Description: In the NEM:BA A&IS Lists (2014, 2016, and 2020) taxa are listed in high-level groupings that correspond to a mix of taxonomic groupings and where the taxa occur. These groupings are included for reference only for taxa that are listed. In a few cases this grouping does not correspond to the kingdom (e.g., some marine algae are listed as marine plants).

Type: Factor with 12 levels (as well as NA for taxa which are not currently listed as per RegulatoryListing)

Value	Definition
Amphibian	
Bird	
Fish.FW	Freshwater fish
Fish.M	Marine fish (there are no alien marine fish recorded from South African waters, but there was one prohibited species in the 2014 and 2016 lists).
Invert.FW	Freshwater invertebrates
Invert.M	Marine invertebrates
Invert.T	Terrestrial invertebrates
Mammal	
Microbe	Microbial species (including all fungi)
Plant.M	Marine plants
Plant.FWT	Terrestrial and freshwater plants
Reptile	

legallyImported

Question addressed: Was the taxon legally brought into South Africa?

Description: Whether permission was given for species to be imported and used outside of a quarantine facility. The criteria for this are as per the regulations.

Relevant indicator(s): HIGH-LEVEL INDICATOR 1

Type: Factor with 5 levels

Value	Definition
NE	Not evaluated.
NA	Historical introductions prior to NEMBA A&IS Regulations or the legality of introductions is otherwise not known.
biocontrol	Species imported and that were permitted by a government department for them to be released.
Legal	An import permit was issued under A&IS Regulations and the species brought in legally for the first time after 2014.
illegal	The species is believed to have been imported for the first time after 2014 without an import permit.

isNative

Question addressed: Is the taxon native to (at least a part) of South Africa?

Description: If a taxon is native to a part of South Africa (i.e. TRUE) then the taxon does not belong in this dataset unless:

- the taxon has, or at some point had, native-alien populations (Nelufule et al. 2022) in South Africa (IntroductionStatus=EstablishedNotInvasive | degreeOfEstablishment=C1-E); or
- the taxon is (or was) prohibited from being introduced to another part of South Africa under regulations; or
- a risk analysis (/assessment) has been conducted on the taxon; or
- the taxon was at some point classified as alien to the whole of South Africa although the taxon's nativity has since been settled and it is clear it is native.

isNative does not align with the Darwin Core variable dwc:establishmentMeans, as terms like introduced confound whether it is alien to a region with dwc:degreeOfEstablishment or the field IntroductionStatus coded here (cf. Groom et al. 2019). For a discussion on the criteria used to classify something as cryptogenic see Essl et al. (2018), with terms as per Carlton (1996) and Richardson et al. (2011). The category of not evaluated as proposed by Essl et al. (2018) is not used here, as if there has been no evaluation of a species' nativity then it also does not belong to this dataset. The category of data deficient as proposed by Essl et al. (2018) is also not used here, and rather all taxa where nativity is highly uncertain are classed as cryptogenic.

Type: Factor with 4 levels.

Value	Definition
Cryptogenic	Those of unknown biogeographic origin, which cannot be definitively categorised as native to any part of South Africa, but neither can be definitively categorised as alien to South Africa where it is present.
FALSE	
TRUE	
DD	An assessment of biogeographic status is unfeasible (data deficient) because of uncertainty in the taxon identity.

Note: There is no valid use of NA, as if nativity has not been evaluated, the taxon should not be included in the dataset. The taxon might be included in an interim dataset in which case the value will be set to 'check', the check must happen before the taxon is incorporated into the actual list.

isNativeConfidence

Description: The level of confidence in the scoring of isNative

Type: Factor with 2 levels (and NA if isNative is Cryptogenic or Data Deficient). A third level is listed in Wilson et al. 2018, but if the nativity is in dispute, and confidence is lower than 90% that it is native to somewhere OR lower than 90% that it is alien everywhere it is, then it should be classed as Cryptogenic.

Value	Definition
high	All databases (at least one of which is authoritative) state that the taxon is native (or alien) and there is no evidence of debate about nativity.
medium	Categorised as native (or alien) in the most authoritative sources although some references report the opposite with no detailed published analysis confirming nativity. OR the only sources in which nativity is recorded are not authoritative.

isNativeSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score isNative

Type: Character or NA

Values: see REFERENCING AND BIBLIOGRAPHY for details

occurrenceStatus

Question addressed: Does the taxon occur in South Africa (as of December 2025)?

Description: This will include both alien and native ranges, for specification of whether it is present as an alien see introductionStatus or degreeOfEstablishment.

Darwin Core: dwc:occurrenceStatus. Not all the values of the vocabulary are used (common, irregular, rare) as information on abundance is stored under organismQuantity.

Relevant indicator(s): 2.1

Type: Factor with 4 levels

Values: Can inherit presences from introductionStatus and degreeOfEstablishment, but can only inherit absences if used in combination with isNative.

Value	Definition
absent	A reasoned analysis of the evidence suggests the taxon is not present in South Africa as of December 2025 OR there is no evidence of presence.
present	There is evidence to document the presence of the taxon in South Africa as of December 2025.
doubtful	There is some evidence of the taxon having been present in South Africa, but there is doubt over the evidence or whether it is still present as of December 2025, including taxonomic or geographic imprecision in the records.
NE	There has been no specific attempt to ascertain if the taxon is in (or has been in) South Africa.

occurrenceStatusConfidence

Description: The level of confidence in the scoring of occurrenceStatus

Type: Factor with 2 levels (and NA if occurrenceStatus is 'doubtful' or 'NotEvaluated'). A third level is listed in Wilson et al. 2018, but if the species has been recorded as present but the record is either questioned or last record from a substantial time ago, then occurrenceStatus should be classed as 'doubtful' and confidence as NA.

Value	Definition
high	For presence: physical sample lodged in a recognised collection identified by an expert OR molecular confirmation of a sample collected in the last 50 years AND field notes in the past decade confirming presence.
	For absence: there is no evidence the taxon is in South Africa despite surveys in relevant areas by individuals with field experience of identifying the taxon, with appropriate sampling AND there are no putative pathways by which it could have recently been introduced OR there is documented evidence declaring eradication / loss of the population, there are no likely putative pathways for recent reintroductions, and it has not been seen for over a decade despite resurveys OR there is a reasoned analysis (e.g., an argument map) that comes to a strong conclusion.
medium	For presence: no physical sample or molecular confirmation, or sample collected over a decade ago with no field confirmations in past ten years.
	For absence: there is no evidence the taxon is in South Africa in the relevant sources OR there is documented evidence declaring eradication / loss of the populations OR there is a reasoned analysis (e.g., an argument map) that comes to a weak conclusion.

occurrenceStatusSource

Description: The reference or source used to score occurrenceStatus, this should include notes on whether there is a physical specimen and a source; whether there is molecular confirmation that the

specimen is that species and provide the source; whether there is a literature record of presence of the specimen and provide source; and whether there has been recent field confirmation and again provide source. In each case the answers are yes, no, unclear (e.g., molecular results might indicate several potential taxa or a field observation might only be to a genus level), or NE (i.e., not evaluated, there has been no attempt to look to see if such data have been collected or not).

Type: Structured text field

Values: 'NE' if occurrenceStatus is NotEvaluated OR

'Physical specimen (yes/no/NE) ref| Molecular confirmation (yes/no/unclear/NE) ref| Literature reference (yes/no/unclear/NE) ref| Field observation (yes/no/unclear/NE) ref'

Example: 'Physical specimen (NE)| Molecular confirmation (NE)| Literature reference (yes) Zachariades (2021)| Field observation (yes) Zachariades (2021)'

degreeOfEstablishment

Question addressed: To what degree is the taxon where it is alien in South Africa surviving, reproducing, and has expanded its range (as of December 2025)?

Description: The coding is taken from the Unified Framework for Biological Invasions (Blackburn et al. 2011) with the wording and description based largely on the Darwin Core term (dwc:degreeOfEstablishment; (Groom et al. 2019)), with the use of native rather than indigenous and the separation of A into A0 and A1 to indicate cases where things have disappeared from South Africa. In cases where it is clear that a taxon can be categorised at a certain level, but it is not clear if it can be categorised at a higher level (e.g., it has certainly established C3, but there isn't clear spread D1, or that the spread results in new self-sustaining populations D2, then it should be scored as C3).

Relevant indicator(s): 2.1.3

Type: Factor with 12 levels (as well as NA):

Value	Definition
A0	Never introduced beyond limits of native range to [a part of] South Africa.
A1	Has been introduced beyond limits of native range to South Africa, but no longer present.
B1	Individuals transported beyond limits of native range, and in captivity or quarantine (i.e., individuals provided with conditions suitable for them, but explicit measures of containment are in place).
B2	Individuals transported beyond limits of native range, and in cultivation (i.e. individuals provided with conditions suitable for them but explicit measures to prevent dispersal are limited at best).
B3	Individuals transported beyond limits of native range, and directly released into novel environment.
C0	Individuals released outside of captivity or cultivation in location where introduced, but incapable of surviving for a significant period.
C1	Individuals surviving outside of captivity or cultivation in location where introduced, no reproduction.
C2	Individuals surviving outside of captivity or cultivation in location where introduced, reproduction occurring, but population not self-sustaining.
C3	Individuals surviving outside of captivity or cultivation in location where introduced, reproduction occurring, and population self-sustaining.

Value	Definition
D1	Self-sustaining population outside of captivity or cultivation, with individuals surviving at a significant distance from the original point of introduction.
D2	Self-sustaining population outside of captivity or cultivation, with individuals surviving and reproducing at a significant distance from the original point of introduction.
E	Fully invasive species, with individuals dispersing, surviving and reproducing at multiple sites across a greater or lesser spectrum of habitats and extent of occurrence.

degreeOfEstablishmentConfidence

Description: The level of confidence in the scoring of degreeOfEstablishment

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if degreeOfEstablishment is NA)

Value	Definition
high	A0–A1: use the criteria for defining absence (occurrenceStatusConfidence) checking against evidence for historical presence (occurrenceStatusConfidence) to separate the two categories.
	B1–D2: based on recent (within the last decade) published field observations specifically using the coding of degreeOfEstablishment.
	E: based on published field observations specifically using the coding of degreeOfEstablishment (regardless of date, as taxa are very unlikely to move from back to D2 or earlier, even despite significant population crashes).
medium	A0–A1: use the criteria for defining absence (occurrenceStatusConfidence) checking against evidence for historical presence (occurrenceStatusConfidence) to separate the two categories.
	B1–E: based on historical (older than the last decade) published field observations with enough detailed information (and demonstrable survey effort) to code them according to degreeOfEstablishment.
low	A0–A1: use the criteria for defining absence (occurrenceStatus AND occurrenceStatusConfidence).
	B1–E: interpreted from distribution data in an atlas project or similar listing project (specify interpretation made in the source, if it is not clear what the survey effort was or if the taxon is correctly identified do not score degreeOfEstablishment).

degreeOfEstablishmentSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score degreeOfEstablishment

Type: Structured text field

Values: Field evaluation using Unified Framework (yes/no), if yes provide a reference, and details of survey method / effort; if no provide distribution dataset that was used and how it was interpreted.

IntroductionStatus

Question addressed: A more basic answer to the question addressed by degreeOfEstablishment: To what degree is the taxon where it is alien in South Africa surviving, reproducing, and has expanded its range (as of December 2025)? This also specifically flags taxa with native-alien populations (sensu Nelufule et al. 2022).

Description: Aligns with high-level introduction status as per the first report. Not part of Darwin Core.

Relevant indicator(s): 2.1.2

Type: Factor with 3 major categories, and 2 sub-categories, as well as NA. Note: can be inherited from degreeOfEstablishment as below:

Value	Definition
NA	If degreeOfEstablishment is A0 or A1 OR if occurrenceStatus is absent or doubtful OR if isNative is TRUE and occurrenceStatus is present, there is no indication of any individuals in what would be considered an alien range OR if it is not evaluated.
presentAsAlienNotEstablished	B1–C2, includes a range of species from those in quarantine to those that are reproducing outside of captivity or cultivation but where there is no clear evidence of having formed self-sustaining populations.
EstablishedNotInvasive	C3–D1, species where there is establishment, and possibly spread, but there is no clear evidence of forming self-sustaining populations at a significant distance from point of introduction.
EstablishedNotInvasive:NativeAlienPopulations	The subcategory NativeAlienPopulations is used in cases where a taxon is native to a part of South Africa but has established populations in another part of South Africa to which the taxon is alien.
Invasive	D2–E, populations are self-sustaining at a significant distance from the point of introduction.
Invasive:NativeAlienPopulations	The subcategory NativeAlienPopulations is used in cases where a taxon is native to a part of South Africa but has formed invasive populations in another part of South Africa to which the taxon is alien.

IntroductionStatusConfidence

Description: The level of confidence in the scoring of IntroductionStatus

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if IntroductionStatus is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Inherited from degreeOfEstablishmentConfidence OR based on recent (within last decade) published field observations.
medium	Inherited from degreeOfEstablishmentConfidence OR based on published field observations older than a decade.
low	Inherited from degreeOfEstablishmentConfidence OR based on expert opinion only with no clear indication of last field observation.

IntroductionStatusSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score IntroductionStatus

Type: Text (and NA if IntroductionStatus is NA)

Values: Either "see degreeOfEstablishmentSource" or provide ref to field observation / expert opinion

pathway

Question addressed: How did (/does) the taxon arrive in its alien range in South Africa?

Description: The field is based on the broad categories which were initially developed by Hulme et al. (2008), with sub-categories adopted by the CBD (Scalera et al. 2016) and later revised (Harrower et al. 2018). For guidance of their application see Harrower et al. (2018). This coding is as per Darwin Core term dwc:pathways v.2021-09-01 <https://dwc.tdwg.org/pw/>.

Relevant indicator(s): 1.2

Type: Factor with 7 major categories, and 44 sub-categories. Nesting is indicated by a colon and multiple levels that apply are separated by a pipe delimiter. For example: releaseInNature:hunting|releaseInNature:landscapImprovement

Values:

Value
releaseInNature
releaseInNature:biologicalControl
releaseInNature:erosionControl
releaseInNature:fisheryInTheWild
releaseInNature:hunting
releaseInNature:landscapImprovement
releaseInNature:conservationOrWildlifeManagement
releaseInNature:releasedForUse
releaseInNature:otherIntentionalRelease
escapeFromConfinement
escapeFromConfinement:agriculture
escapeFromConfinement:aquacultureMariculture
escapeFromConfinement:publicGardenZooAquaria
escapeFromConfinement:pet
escapeFromConfinement:farmedAnimals
escapeFromConfinement:forestry
escapeFromConfinement:fur
escapeFromConfinement:horticulture
escapeFromConfinement:ornamentalNonHorticulture
escapeFromConfinement:research
escapeFromConfinement:liveFoodLiveBait
escapeFromConfinement:otherEscape
transportContaminant
transportContaminant:contaminantNursery

Value
transportContaminant:contaminateBait
transportContaminant:foodContaminant
transportContaminant:contaminantOnAnimals
transportContaminant:parasitesOnAnimals
transportContaminant:contaminantOnPlants
transportContaminant:parasitesOnPlants
transportContaminant:seedContaminant
transportContaminant:timberTrade
transportContaminant:transportationHabitatMaterial
transportStowaway
transportStowaway:fishingEquipment
transportStowaway:containerBulk
transportStowaway:hitchhikersAirplane
transportStowaway:hitchhikersShip
transportStowaway:machineryEquipment
transportStowaway:people
transportStowaway:packingMaterial
transportStowaway:ballastWater
transportStowaway:hullFouling
transportStowaway:vehicles
transportStowaway:otherTransport
corridor
corridor:waterwaysBasinsSeas
corridor:tunnelsBridges
unaided
unaided:naturalDispersal
unknown

pathwayConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable pathway was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if pathway is Unknown)

Value	Definition
high	Direct evidence that it was introduced along a pathway.
medium	Indirect evidence (e.g., correlation between pathway and sites in the country).
low	Inferred based on species traits and/or other regions.

pathwaySource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the pathway for a given taxon

Type: Text

Values: reference(s)

eventDateIntroduction

Question addressed: When was the taxon first introduced as an alien to South Africa?

Description: The year in which the taxon was first introduced to South Africa (i.e. dwc:eventDate). In some definitions introduction is taken to be the first record outside of captivity or cultivation (cf. IPBES IAS Assessment), however here we take the literal approach, i.e., the date when a taxon is first introduced to the country at the border. Introductions thus include taxa which are brought into quarantine (and might never be released). Additional eventDates might be added in future that are closer to the sense in which IPBES has used the term (e.g., date of first record of establishment). Should conform to ISO 8601:2004(E), noting the standard allows for date ranges. This is not, necessarily, the same as the date of first record, though obviously the date of first record provides an important estimate for this.

Relevant indicator(s): 1.2, 2.1

Type: An ordered factor with potential levels up to 31 December 2025.

Values: Any dates before the current era (i.e., BC) are marked as negative.

eventDateIntroductionConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable eventDateIntroduction was scored for a given taxon. There are two aspects that determine this confidence level. First the degree of confidence that the first record was a real record, and second how close to the date of introduction was the first record.

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if eventDateIntroduction is NA)

Value	Definition
high	There is reliable evidence both that the taxon was recorded in that year (e.g., from herbarium records or DNA samples) AND that the taxon was not introduced earlier. This could include records of deliberate introductions of organisms that would not otherwise arrive accidentally. The estimate is highly likely to be within 2 years of the actual date of introduction.
medium	There is strong evidence that a taxon was recorded that year / date range, but there could have been earlier records. OR The evidence that the taxon was recorded that year / date range is weak, but it is unlikely that there could have been earlier records. OR The site of first detection is associated with a likely introduction pathway that can be assigned to a particular date range. The estimate is highly likely to be within 20 years of the actual date.
low	The first record of the taxon is disputed and only much more recently do reliable records confirm presence. OR It is highly possible that introductions were occurring but the taxon was not detected as there was no explicit search efforts in place. The estimate is likely to be decades from the actual date.

Note: Importantly there are a few caveats to this value. First when a taxon was first introduced to South Africa might be much earlier than date of the introduction that subsequently led to an established and/or invasive population (many introductions fail). Second, the first record depends on the search effort, this is not explicitly measured here but could potentially be. For example, if a pest was not previously intercepted at the border despite border inspections being in place, but shortly after the first interceptions were recorded the pest was found to have established in the field, it

could be assumed that border inspections would have picked up introductions. The first interception therefore provides evidence that introductions were occurring, there is evidence that the taxon was detectable, and the search in this case was probably appropriate, though of course the exact date of introduction that led to the establishment is not known.

eventDateIntroductionSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the eventDateIntroduction for a given taxon

Type: Text

Values: reference(s)

RangeBroadAdmin

Question addressed: How widespread is the alien taxon outside of captivity/cultivation in South Africa—in terms of broad administrative regions?

Description: This lists the occupancy of specific administrative regions (the nine provinces; 22 water management areas for freshwater systems; and seven marine ecoregions), noting that the Prince Edward Islands are not included here as they have their own separate files for species list and metadata.

Relevant indicator(s): 2.2.1

Type: A factor with 37 levels (and NA if there is no range OR if the range is not known with this level of precision).

Values: Multiple levels that apply are separated by a pipe delimiter.

Value	Definition
EC	Eastern Cape Province
FS	Free-State Province
GP	Gauteng Province
KZN	KwaZulu Natal Province
LP	Limpopo Province
MP	Mpumalanga Province
NC	Northern Cape Province
NW	North-West Province
WC	Western Cape Province
WMAA– WMAX	the 22 National Water Management Areas, labelled A to X
SB	Southern Benguela marine ecoregion
AG	Agulhas marine ecoregion
NT	Natal marine ecoregion
DL	Delagoa marine ecoregion
SEA	Southeast Atlantic marine ecoregion
SWI	Southwest Indian marine ecoregion

RangeBroadAdminConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable RangeBroadAdmin was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if RangeBroadAdmin is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Included in a formal verified atlas or mapping project based on recent surveys with adequate ground-truthing. There is some indication that there have been surveys at sites where the taxon is not recorded as present.
medium	Data from an atlas project, though it is not explicit that sites where it is not recorded as present would have been recorded/some sites might not have been surveyed.
low	Interpreted from expert opinion.

RangeBroadAdminSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the RangeBroadAdmin for a given taxon

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

RangeBroadEcol

Question addressed: How widespread is the alien taxon outside of captivity/cultivation in South Africa—in terms of broad ecological regions?

Description: This lists the occupancy of specific biogeographic regions (the biomes for terrestrial systems; for freshwater systems; and six marine ecoregions as per Sink et al. (2012), noting that this excludes the Prince Edward Island marine ecoregion).

Relevant indicator(s): 2.2.1

Type: A factor with multiple levels (and NA if there is no range OR if the range is not known with this level of precision). Multiple levels that apply are separated by a pipe delimiter.

Values: if a factor with several levels as a table (e.g., for confidence levels)

Value	Definition
AT	Terrestrial ecoregion – Albany Thicket
Aza, AZd, AZe	Terrestrial ecoregion – Azonal Vegetation
D	Terrestrial ecoregion – Desert
FO	Terrestrial ecoregion – Forests
FF, FR, FS	Terrestrial ecoregion – Fynbos
G	Terrestrial ecoregion – Grassland
CB	Terrestrial ecoregion – Indian Ocean Coastal Belt
AZf, AZi, Azm, AZs	Terrestrial ecoregion – Inland Azonal Vegetation
NK	Terrestrial ecoregion – Nama-Karoo
SV	Terrestrial ecoregion – Savanna
SK	Terrestrial ecoregion – Succulent Karoo
CT	Estuarine – Cool temperate
ST	Estuarine – Subtropical

Value	Definition
TR	Estuarine – Tropical
WT	Estuarine – Warm Temperate
SB	Marine ecoregion – Benguela
AG	Marine ecoregion – Agulhas
NT	Marine ecoregion – Natal
DL	Marine ecoregion – Delagoa
SEA	Marine ecoregion – Southeast Atlantic
SWI	Marine ecoregion – Southwest Indian

RangeBroadEcolConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable RangeBroadEcol was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if RangeBroadEcol is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Included in a formal verified atlas or mapping project based on recent surveys with adequate ground-truthing. There is some indication that there have been surveys at sites where the taxon is not recorded as present.
medium	Data from an atlas project, though it is not explicit that sites where it is not recorded as present would have been recorded/some sites might not have been surveyed.
low	Interpreted from expert opinion.

RangeBroadEcolSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the RangeBroadEcol for a given taxon

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

RangeQDGC

Question addressed: How widespread is the alien taxon outside of captivity/cultivation in South Africa—in terms of quarter-degree grid cells?

Description: The number of quarter-degree grid cells (QDGCs) occupied by the taxon in its alien range (for where they are found, consult the data sources)

Relevant indicator(s): 2.2.2

Type: Integer

Values: 1–total number of QDGCs occupied depending on the QDGC level used (specify QDGC level) or NA if there is no range or if not known with this level of precision

RangeQDGCConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable RangeQDGC was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if RangeQDGC is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Included in a formal verified atlas or mapping project based on recent surveys with adequate ground-truthing. There is some indication that there have been surveys at sites where the taxon is not recorded as present.
medium	Data from an atlas project, though it is not explicit that sites where it is not recorded as present would have been recorded/some sites might not have been surveyed.
low	Interpreted from expert opinion.

RangeQDGCSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the RangeQDGC for a given taxon

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

RangeExact

Question addressed: How widespread is the alien taxon outside of captivity/cultivation in South Africa—in terms of area occupied?

Description: An estimate of the area occupied by the species at a specific resolution

Relevant indicator(s): 2.2.3

Type: Numeric or NA if there is no range or if not known with this level of precision

Values: depends on RangeExactType

RangeExactType

Description: The units in which the range is presented (e.g., ha, km of coastline, rivers)

Type: Factor

Values: levels to be determined and modified as data added e.g., ha—occupied area in terms of hectares putting a polygon around point patterns of individual discrete populations

RangeExactConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable RangeExact was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if RangeExact is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Data based on a project within the last decade specifically designed to map the range of the taxon in question, with search effort explicit and sufficient to determine where taxa are and where they are not. Might include citizen science component for easily identified taxa. Appropriate statistical technique used to estimate total range size (particular if disjunct distributions).
medium	Data from atlas project or general mapping project with indication of sampling effort, but data not complete or not recent (e.g., >10 years old).
low	No absence data, no clear statistical methodology for estimating range size, or very broad estimate.

RangeExactSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score RangeExact for a given taxon

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

RangeFreeText

Question addressed: How widespread is the alien taxon outside of captivity/cultivation in South Africa—text description of current range?

Description: Notes as to the range can be made, e.g., if it is restricted only to specific habitats like urban areas or harbours

Relevant indicator(s): 2.2

Type: Character or NA

RangeFreeTextSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score RangeFreeText for a given taxon

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

organismQuantityCategorical

Question addressed: How abundant is the taxon in its alien range in South Africa as of December 2025—is there a qualitative measure per spatial unit?

Description: Categorical measure of abundance per species per locality, with localities defined using organismQuantityCategoricalType (cf. dwc:organismQuantity and dwc:organismQuantityType)

Relevant indicator(s): 2.3.1

Type: Factor with 3 levels

Value	Definition
TRUE	An evaluation of abundance based on (absent; rare; occasional; abundant) has been made for the alien taxon at -at least- some of the localities where it occurs.
FALSE	
NA	It is not present.

organismQuantityCategoricalType

Description: the spatial unit(s) for which data on quantities are available

Type: Factor

Values: levels to be determined and modified as data added, e.g., provinces, or protected areas

organismQuantityCategoricalConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable organismQuantityCategorical was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if organismQuantityCategorical is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Recent survey, technique used well documented, and several people confirming the value obtained (e.g., included in a formal verified atlas or mapping project based on recent surveys with adequate ground-truthing).
medium	Data from an atlas project or recent survey but only one person.
low	Interpreted from expert opinion, or no clear basis for the value given, or over 10 years ago.

organismQuantityCategoricalSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score organismQuantityCategorical for a given taxon

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

organismQuantityExact

Question addressed: How abundant is the taxon in its alien range in South Africa—in terms of an exact overall number?

Description: An estimate of the area occupied by the species at a specific resolution, or numbers of individuals

Relevant indicator(s): 2.3.2

Type: Numeric

organismQuantityExactType

Description: The type of data of organismQuantityExact

Type: Factor with 2 levels (and NA if organismQuantityExact is NA)

Values: if a factor with several levels as a table (e.g., for confidence levels)

Value	Definition
numind	Number of individuals
cca	Condensed canopy area in ha

organismQuantityExactConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable organismQuantityExact was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA if organismQuantityExact is NA)

Value	Definition
high	Accurate and recent population census, using appropriate statistical techniques.
medium	Estimation based on sampling that uses assumptions and makes extrapolations.
low	Expert opinion.

organismQuantityExactSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score organismQuantityExact for a given taxon

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

organismQuantityDetailed

Question addressed: How abundant is the taxon in its alien range in South Africa—are detailed information available on individuals?

Description: Are detailed data available e.g., on the sizes, ages, or condition of individuals, that make up the population

Relevant indicator(s): 2.3.3

Type: Factor with 2 levels

Values: TRUE or FALSE

organismQuantityDetailedSource

Description: The reference or sources where data on organismQuantity area available

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

impactEICATSouthAfrica

Question addressed: How severe are the most severe recorded negative environmental impacts of the alien taxon in South Africa?

Description: A single value should be given which is the maximum recorded environmental impact in South Africa (Blackburn et al. 2014; Hawkins et al. 2015; IUCN 2020).

Relevant indicator(s): 2.4

Type: Factor with 7 levels (including NA if there is no alien population and NE if it has not been evaluated within the context of the report)

Value	Definition
MC	Minimal Concern
MN	Minor
MO	Moderate
MR	Major
MV	Massive
DD	Data Deficient
NA	No Alien population
NE	Not Evaluated

impactEICATSouthAfricaConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable impactEICATSouthAfrica was scored for a given taxon. Guidance regarding the use of the confidence rating is taken from Hawkins et al. (2015) as modified therein from the EPPO pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Alan MacLeod 09/03/2011; revised 28/04/2011; copied from CAPRA, version 2.74; 2).

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	Approximately 90% chance of assessment being correct. There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment; and impacts are recorded at the typical spatial scale over which original native communities can be characterised; and there are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa; and the interpretation of data/information is straightforward; and data/information are not controversial or contradictory; and the assessment was approved by the IUCN EICAT Unit or similar.
medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which may not be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty; and/or the interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory; and the assessment used the IUCN EICAT reporting templates or similar.
low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g., only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or to embrace significant uncertainties; and/or evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g., because it is strongly ambiguous; and/or the information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable; and the assessment did not use the IUCN EICAT reporting templates or similar.

impactEICATSouthAfricaSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score impactEICATSouthAfrica for a given taxon. The reference should be to the impact assessment conducted rather than to all the primary sources.

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

impactEICAT

Question addressed: How severe might the negative environmental impacts of the alien taxon be?

Description: A single value should be given which is the maximum recorded environmental impact in any alien range of the taxon (Blackburn et al. 2014; Hawkins et al. 2015; IUCN 2020). This is included here to give an indication of which taxa are known to cause damage. Note, this does not assess the

likelihood of similar impacts being realised in South Africa (e.g., it does not take into account climatic suitability and environmental context), although information from South Africa might be used in the assessment.

Type: Factor with 7 levels (including NA, note if data aren't available this is NE)

Value	Definition
MC	Minimal Concern
MN	Minor
MO	Moderate
MR	Major
MV	Massive
DD	Data Deficient
NA	No Alien population
NE	Not Evaluated

impactEICATConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable impactEICAT was scored for a given taxon.

Guidance regarding the use of the confidence rating is taken from Hawkins et al. (2015) as modified therein from the EPPO pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Alan MacLeod 09/03/2011; revised 28/04/2011; copied from CAPRA, version 2.74; 2).

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	Approximately 90% chance of assessment being correct. There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment; and impacts are recorded at the typical spatial scale over which original native communities can be characterised; and there are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa; and the interpretation of data/information is straightforward; and data/information are not controversial or contradictory; and the assessment was approved by the IUCN EICAT Unit or similar.
medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which may not be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty; and/or the interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory; and the assessment used the IUCN EICAT reporting templates or similar.
low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g., only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or to embrace significant uncertainties; and/or evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g., because it is strongly ambiguous; and/or the information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable; and the assessment did not use the IUCN EICAT reporting templates or similar

impactEICATSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score impactEICAT for a given taxon. The reference should be to the impact assessment conducted rather than to all the primary sources.

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

impactSEICATSouthAfrica

Question addressed: How severe are the most severe recorded negative socio-economic impacts of the alien taxon in South Africa?

Description: A single value should be given which is the maximum recorded socio-economic impact in South Africa (Bacher et al. 2018).

Relevant indicator(s): 2.4

Type: Factor with 7 levels (including NA, note if data aren't available this is NE)

Value	Definition
MC	Minimal Concern
MN	Minor
MO	Moderate
MR	Major
MV	Massive
DD	Data Deficient
NA	No Alien Population
NE	Not Evaluated

impactSEICATSouthAfricaConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable impactSEICATSouthAfrica was scored for a given taxon. Guidance regarding the use of the confidence rating is taken from Hawkins et al. (2015) as modified therein from the EPPO pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Alan MacLeod 09/03/2011; revised 28/04/2011; copied from CAPRA, version 2.74; 2).

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	Approximately 90% chance of assessment being correct. There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment; and impacts are recorded at the typical spatial scale over which original native communities can be characterised; and there are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa; and the interpretation of data/information is straightforward; and data/information are not controversial or contradictory; and the assessment was approved by the IUCN EICAT Unit or similar.

Value	Definition
medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which may not be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty; and/or the interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory; and the assessment used the IUCN EICAT reporting templates or similar.
low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g., only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or to embrace significant uncertainties; and/or evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g., because it is strongly ambiguous; and/or the information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable; and the assessment did not use the IUCN EICAT reporting templates or similar.

impactSEICATSouthAfricaSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score impactSEICATSouthAfrica for a given taxon. The reference should be to the impact assessment conducted rather than to all the primary sources.

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

impactSEICAT

Question addressed: How severe might the negative socio-economic impacts of the alien taxon be?

Description: A single value should be given which is the maximum recorded socio-economic impact in any alien range of the taxon (Bacher et al., 2018). Note, this does not assess the likelihood of similar impacts being realised in South Africa (e.g., it does not take into account climatic suitability and environmental context), although information from South Africa might be used in the assessment.

Type: Factor with 7 levels (including NA, note if data aren't available this is NE)

Value	Definition
MC	Minimal Concern
MN	Minor
MO	Moderate
MR	Major
MV	Massive
DD	Data Deficient
NA	No Alien Population
NE	Not Evaluated

impactSEICATConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable impactSEICAT was scored for a given taxon. Guidance regarding the use of the confidence rating is taken from Hawkins et al. (2015) as modified therein from the EPPO pest risk assessment decision support scheme (Alan MacLeod 09/03/2011; revised 28/04/2011; copied from CAPRA, version 2.74; 2).

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	Approximately 90% chance of assessment being correct. There is direct relevant observational evidence to support the assessment; and impacts are recorded at the typical spatial scale over which original native communities can be characterised; and there are reliable/good quality data sources on impacts of the taxa; and the interpretation of data/information is straightforward; and data/information are not controversial or contradictory; and the assessment was approved by the IUCN EICAT Unit or similar.
medium	There is some direct observational evidence to support the assessment, but some information is inferred; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which may not be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, but extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered reliable, or to embrace little uncertainty; and/or the interpretation of the data is to some extent ambiguous or contradictory; and the assessment used the IUCN EICAT reporting templates or similar.
low	There is no direct observational evidence to support the assessment, e.g., only inferred data have been used as supporting evidence; and/or impacts are recorded at a spatial scale which is unlikely to be relevant to the scale over which original native communities can be characterized, and extrapolation or downscaling of the data to relevant scales is considered unreliable or to embrace significant uncertainties; and/or evidence is poor and difficult to interpret, e.g., because it is strongly ambiguous; and/or the information sources are considered to be of low quality or contain information that is unreliable; and the assessment did not use the IUCN EICAT reporting templates or similar.

impactSEICATSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score impactSEICAT for a given taxon. The reference should be to the impact assessment conducted rather than to all the primary sources.

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

impactExpertOpinion

Question addressed: How do experts rank the negative impacts of alien taxon in South Africa in 2015?

Description: This was used for the first report, but is deprecated in future reports as it is not transparent (Zengeya et al. 2017).

Type: Factor with 7 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
Severe	~Massive
Major	~Major
Some	~Moderate
Few	~Minor
Negligible	Minimal Concern
DD	Data Deficient
NE	Not Evaluated

RiskAnalysis

Question addressed: Has a risk analysis of the alien taxon been completed for South Africa?

Description: Whether a risk analysis has been completed for the taxon according to the Risk Analysis for Alien Taxa (RAAT) framework (Kumschick et al. 2020), approved by the Alien Species Risk Analysis Review Panel, and submitted to DFFE

Relevant indicator(s): 4.1, 4.3, 4.5, 4.8

Type: Factor with 2 levels

Values: TRUE or FALSE

RiskAnalysisSource

Description: The reference that was used to score RiskAnalysis

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s), ideally to a document with a doi

RiskAssessmentCompleted

Description: Whether a 'risk assessment' (in some cases technically a risk analysis) has been submitted to DFFE on the taxon, this might be in support of an import application and so would need to include information specified in the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations, however, there is no set framework for such documents. In the case of import application the 'risk assessment' (technically a risk analysis) might have been reviewed by SANBI and maybe also ASRARP. It is a requirement of the status report to report on species for which a 'risk assessment' has been completed.

Type: Factor with 2 levels

Values: TRUE or FALSE

PermitsGranted

Question addressed: Have permits been issued for the use of the alien taxon in South Africa?

Description: It is a requirement of the status report to provide details of taxa for which permits have been issued. This specifies the number of permits issued since the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations were promulgated. For details see the permit database (the latest version should be accessible by looking at <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947810> for updates) A taxon may have permit issued for it for

research or other purposes, and a taxon may have change in regulatory status other time and permits are no longer required.

Relevant indicator(s): 4.1

Type: Numeric

PermitsRefused

Question addressed: Have permits been issued for the use of the alien taxon in South Africa?

Description: It is a requirement of the status report to provide details of taxa for which permits have been refused. This specifies the number of permits refused since the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations were promulgated. This has not previously been included in the permit database but it is intended to be added to future versions (the latest version should be accessible by looking at <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947810> for updates). A permit may have been refused for administrative issues rather than specific concerns over invasiveness and so the number of permits refused must be interpreted with caution.

Relevant indicator(s): 4.1

Type: Numeric

speciesTreated

Question addressed: Has the taxon been subject to control efforts in South Africa between 1 January 2023 and 31 December 2025?

Description: If there are records of management having been implemented.

Relevant indicator(s): 4.5

Type: Factor with three levels

Value	Definition
NE	There has not been an evaluation of whether management has been implemented.
no	No populations were managed.
yes	One or more populations have had some management.

speciesTreatedConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable speciesTreated was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA).

Value	Definition
high	There are readily available, up-to-date, records that management has (or has not) been applied to the species within the reporting period, and similarly that biocontrol agents have (or have not) established and are still present.
medium	Records of management (or a lack of management) are cited in other reports but were not available to be scrutinised. In the case of biocontrol agents, the level of confidence would depend on the level of evidence that the agents had established in the field.
low	There are indications that previous recorded attempts to control the species prior to the reporting period (i.e., >3 years ago) have continued or were discontinued, but no details are available beyond personal communications.

speciesTreatedSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score speciesTreated for a given taxon

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

speciesTreatedEffect

Question addressed: If the taxon has been subject to control efforts in South Africa during the time period, how effective have these control efforts been relative to a situation where there was no control?

Description: Outcome indicator for management based in part on that developed for assessing the efficacy of classical biological control programmes (Klein, 2011), and specifically the extent to which management is needed to maintain populations below a set threshold.

Relevant indicator(s): 4.8

Type: Factor with seven levels

Value	Definition
NA	The taxon has not been subjected to treatment, or whether it has been subjected to treatment is not known, i.e. speciesTreated is NE or none.
NE	There has been some treatment, but the effectiveness of such has not been evaluated or is otherwise not known.
counter-productive	There is evidence that control has led to further spread; has caused increases in abundance; and/or has made subsequent treatments more difficult without reducing the invasion.
ineffective	The extent of the invasion or the abundance of the species has continued to increase at rates that would have been expected if no control had been applied.
partial	Rate of increase in extent or abundance has slowed.
effective	Extent or abundance is decreasing or has ended up below a management threshold, but management is still required to maintain the populations below the threshold.
permanent	There is no more active management and despite this the population remains below the management threshold.
eradicated	The taxon has been successfully eradicated from South Africa.

speciesTreatedEffectConfidence

Description: The confidence with which the variable speciesTreatedEffect was scored for a given taxon

Type: Factor with 3 levels (and NA)

Value	Definition
high	There has been a published peer-reviewed quantitative assessment of the degree of control achieved.
medium	There is a report that is based on monitoring data.
low	Expert opinion.

speciesTreatedEffectSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score speciesTreatedEffect for a given taxon

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s)

realm

Question addressed: Which 'realm' is the species adapted to?

Description: This column is to enable cross-compatibility with South Africa's National Biodiversity Assessment process, and the allowed values are taken from here. This is a species level property and not a property of the invasion itself. To work out which taxa are invasive in a given realm, need to link to degreeOfEstablishment or introductionStatus. This is not taken directly from RegulatoryGrouping, in part as the values do not align (e.g., RegulatoryGrouping has freshwater, realm has InIndAqu).

Note that 'coastal' is not a realm, but a zone in which the marine, estuarine and terrestrial realms meet, and therefore coastal taxa will be marine and / or terrestrial and / or estuarine depending on their preferences.

Type: Factor with 4 levels and any combination of these levels (and NA if it has not been classified). Multiple levels that apply are separated by a pipe delimiter.

Value	Definition
Estuarine	Inhabits estuarine systems.
InIndAqu	Inhabits inland aquatic systems (including freshwater lentic and lotic).
M	Inhabits marine ecosystems, including both pelagic and benthic.
T	Inhabits terrestrial ecosystems, note no separation is made for edaphic or aerial taxa.

realmSource

Description: The reference or sources that were used to score the realm for a given taxon

Type: Character or NA

Values: reference(s), in this case it is acceptable to reference the NBA and the references contained therein.